

Celebrating Cybersecurity Month — ENSEMBLE's October Recap

What's New at ENSEMBLE? | October's Edition | Newsletter

Celebrating Cybersecurity Month - October Recap

In line with **European Cybersecurity Month**, the ENSEMBLE project continues its work to develop robust, collaborative tools to support the fight against digital crime. This month, we were privileged to present one of our first practical training modules: the ENSEMBLE Serious Game, designed to enhance the training of individuals and organisations in combating malware. In addition, we have joined the LEA Projects Cluster. This alliance has allowed us to actively participate in crucial round tables and workshops (both in Madrid and online), where we seek to share knowledge.

The screenshot shows a game menu for "The Adventures of Anti-Virus Man". It features a grid of six game options, each with a "SUMMARY" button below it:

- Play Worm Attack (with a pink worm icon)
- Play Botnet Zombies (with three blue robot icons)
- Play Trojan Torment (with a Trojan horse icon and question marks)
- Play Spy Race (with three blue spy icons)
- Play Ransom Run (with a skull and crossbones icon)
- Play Ad-Man (with a man in a hat icon)

On the right side, there is an "About" button and a "How to Play" section with the following instructions:

How to Play

Use the arrow keys/WSAD to navigate around the maze.

Grab the question marks and answer all the questions to power up, before the malware consumes all your data.

Once powered up, catch and remove all the malware to free your system!

At the bottom right, there are logos for ENSEMBLE and CENTRIC.

Combating Malware with ENSEMBLE's First Serious Game

23th October

In the latest blog post, [James Fenwick](#) from [CENTRIC](#) announces how the [ENSEMBLE](#) Project is raising awareness about malware and prevention through its first serious game.

To coincide with European Cybersecurity Month, [ENSEMBLE](#) is proud to announce the launch of “[The Adventures of Anti-Virus Man](#)”, a web-based game designed to provide fun, engaging, and bite-sized learning experiences. The game aims to increase players' knowledge of the different types of *malware* and, importantly, what to do if *malware* has infiltrated the user's system. This is a key initiative to promote digital hygiene and help individuals and organizations strengthen their cybersecurity practices.

[Learn more](#)

Strategic Collaboration: Key Takeaways from the Joint Workshop in Madrid & LEA Cluster Meeting

24th and 29th October

The [ENSEMBLE](#) project reinforced its engagement with the research and security community through two key collaborative events held in October.

The first was the online LEA Projects Cluster Meeting on Friday, October 24, 2025. [ENSEMBLE](#) was officially welcomed as a new member at this event, co-hosted by [Privanova](#) and [SafeHorizon](#), which featured prominent presentations by experts such as Fu Huanzhang from the [INTERPOL Innovation Centre](#). This strategic forum focused on cybercrime, artificial intelligence, and future security challenges.

Taking advantage of European Cybersecurity Month, the collaboration continued with a networking workshop held in Madrid, where [ENSEMBLE](#) co-hosted the session alongside [PRESERVE](#), [SafeHorizon Project EU](#), and the LEA Projects Cluster. This gathering brought together LEAs and researchers to discuss trends in *malware*, the funding of illicit activities, and the challenges of cross-border cooperation and AI in investigations.

[Learn more](#)

BONUS INSIGHT JUST FOR YOU

Dissecting the Modus Operandi of Ransomware: A Behavioral and Economic Analysis

Dr. [Francesco Zola](#) from [Vicomtech](#) delivered a lecture at Luxembourg University. During the lecture, we discussed how NLP and ML can be used to analyze interactions between ransomware operators and victims to extract the ransomware playbook. Furthermore, we discussed how different ransomware strains

share similar money laundering mechanisms, based on their transactions within the cryptocurrency ecosystem.

Learn more

ENSEMBLE at 19ENISE

[Germán Esteban López](#) from [Byron Labs](#) participated in the Speaker Corner at the [19ENISE](#) event. His practical demonstration focused on using cyber intelligence to trace threats, analyze the impact of compromised data (using the SpainData leak as an example), and the application of intelligence techniques for information correlation and situational awareness. This demonstration highlighted how essential these specialized tools are for providing timely, useful information in response to complex security challenges.

Learn more

We appreciate your interest in ENSEMBLE. Please feel free to share this newsletter with colleagues who may wish to follow our progress. More updates coming soon!